

Research Article

Inside the Mind of Cybercriminals: Investigating the Influence of Socioeconomic Factors on the Ethical Decision-Making of Cybercriminals

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Abstract: Cybercriminals engage in illicit actions and purposefully exploit weaknesses in computer systems, networks, and users' information for personal benefits. Their activities are unethical by definition since they violate the ideals of privacy, integrity, and honesty. Ethical behaviour considers the repercussions of one's actions, respect the rights and well-being of others, and adhere to society norms and legal systems. Unethical behaviour has substantial consequences towards people, organisations and nations. Cybercriminals, by definition, put their own interests before ethical concerns. It was discovered that in this digital era, most internet users have been impacted by the ramifications of digital manipulation strategies such as scamming, luring, misleading information on social media and et cetera. The altering or modification of digital material, such as photographs, videos, audio, or text, to intentionally deceive or mislead the audience is referred to as digital manipulation. It entails the use of digital tools and software to alter the original information in ways ranging from modest upgrades to outright fabrications. In this study, we gathered material by collecting research papers via online databases as well as utilising the Google search engine to acquire definitions and case studies connected to the topic. This paper has identified factors that are influencing the ethical behaviours of perpetrators to perform such devious acts upon other users. Some of these factors were for profit motive, unaware of the consequences, anonymity, peer influences or subcultures and user dependency on technologies. We also constructed a conceptual framework at the end of the research to analyse the relationship between factors of cyber-crimes and the ethical behaviour of perpetrators.

Keywords: Ethical Behavior; Cybercriminal; Digital Manipulation.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8180744

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1. INTRODUCTION

In an era dominated by technology and the widespread accessibility of information, the power of digital manipulation has emerged as formidable challenges. The rapid emergence of digital tools and platforms has transformed how people interact, exchange ideas, and consume information. However, these developments bring with them a risk: the distortion, manipulation, and propagation of false narratives on an unprecedented scale.

Digital manipulation refers to a variety of fraudulent tactics used to change, manipulate, or distort digital material such as photos, videos, audio recordings, and text. Individuals or groups may change visual and audio aspects with astounding accuracy when equipped with advanced editing tools, blurring the border between truth and illusion. Manipulation can range from harmless upgrades to more subtle deceptions designed to manipulate public perception, destroy trust, or advance personal or political objectives. In the modern digital age, ethical behaviour towards data manipulation is critical. Given individuals and organisations have access to huge amounts of data and the ability to broadcast information globally, ethical standards must be followed in order to maintain trust, integrity, and social well-being.

As technology has become more sophisticated over the previous decade, complaints of cybercriminal activities have surged. In comparison to 2010, there have been approximately 4.7 million reports of cybercrime in 2020. This sudden growth will cost the economy trillions. Cybercriminals are growing more devious as they evolve. Their attack vectors are continually altering dependent on the targets they chose. The perpetrators utilised a variety of strategies, including internet scamming, luring, identity theft, online sexual harassment, distributing false information and more. These strategies can have influence on enterprises, degrade other people's reputations, and misuse other people's information for personal gain. Hence, it is of the utmost importance that users become cognizant of the current cybercrime events that have been plaguing nations throughout the world and take measures to prevent being victimised.

The study and application of ethical concepts and values in connection to the gathering, dissemination, storage, and use of information is referred to as information ethics. It includes ethical issues and obligations related to information technology, digital media, data privacy, intellectual property, and information access. Information ethics aids in the development of trust in digital systems, organisations, and institutions. It promotes public trust and confidence by encouraging openness, accountability, and ethical behaviour in the processing of information, as well as investigating the larger social and ethical implications of information technology. This examines themes such as cyberbullying, online harassment, disinformation, and the influence of digital technology on social interactions, democracy, and human rights.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study was carried out by collecting research papers from online databases as well as references from the internet, including case examples correlating with the subject under discussion and developing a conceptual research model.

2.1. Research Paper Collection

We discovered quite a number of research articles that investigate the same topic as our discourse. These articles serve as our references for additional understanding and discussion, allowing our readers to grasp the fundamental goal of our research. These materials were obtained via numerous online databases, including Emerald, Scopus, and even Google Scholar.

2.2. Google Search Engine

We managed to seek out definitions and sample cases related to the stated topic through the use of the Google search engine. By doing so, we were able to justify our arguments based on the findings that were provided by Google.

2.3. Conceptual Framework

We developed a conceptual framework, to show the correlation between the factors of cybercrimes which included (profit motive, anonymity, peer influenced and subcultures, user dependency on technology and unaware of the consequences) and the ethical behaviour of perpetrators.

3. FINDINGS

According to our research, we uncovered a variety of attributes that affected cybercriminals' ethical behaviour in carrying out such deceitful crimes on their victims. The above attributes included:

3.1 Profit Motive

For cybercriminals, financial gain is a powerful motivator. The possibility of making rapid and large earnings through acts such as hacking, identity theft, ransomware, or fraud can lead to persons prioritising selfish gain over ethical considerations. According to (Mohd Zaharon and Mohd Ali, 2021) Malaysian authorities have seen an upsurge in cybercrime phishing incidents, which result in large monetary losses. A different case in fact is the Central Bank of Malaysia (BNM), which recorded a loss of 0.00002% on any financial transaction as a result of phishing schemes. (Sharifah er al., 2019). These perpetrators employ a variety of tactics to entice their victims into their schemes. For instance, phishing which is "an act of deception whereby impersonation is used to obtain information from a target" (Lastdrager, 2014). Phishing attacks are the fifth most prevalent source of security breaches and have the greatest success rate. (Verison, 2019). Cybercrimes such as internet scams, frauds, or phishing can result in criminal penalties under the Personal Data Act 2010. Penalties may differ based on the amount of money involved, the number of victims, and the perpetrator's purpose. Convictions in some situations can result in three years in prison, penalties, or both.

Furthermore, since the emergence of COVID-19, online purchase fraud cases in Malaysia have escalated dramatically during the Movement Control Order (MCO). Cybercriminals may target people, organisations, or even governments in order to gain sensitive information such as credit card numbers, bank account information, or personal information, which may then be monetized in a variety of ways. It was reported in Malaysia, where 6187 people were scammed by online vendors (Bavani, 2020). Profiteering, not showing pricing, false representation and deceiving consumers about items, selling counterfeit goods and services that have already been paid for, and pyramid scheme-type businesses were among the cases. Thus, it is important that consumers acknowledge the neverending fraud cases in order to avoid falling victim to online scams. By providing sufficient education on the importance of cybersecurity and raising awareness of scamming concerns, the number of scamming incidents would gradually decrease.

3.2 Unaware of the Consequences

In other circumstances, cybercriminals may believe they are unlikely to be detected or face legal penalties for their crimes. Because of the global nature of cybercrime, jurisdictional problems, and differing enforcement capacities across nations, cybercriminals may believe they may act with impunity. One of the motives that prompted these offenders to perform such atrocities was the rapidly evolving nature of cybercrimes that often outpaces the development of legal frameworks and enforcement mechanisms. Existing laws may not effectively handle new types of cyberattacks or strategies, making it harder to prosecute hackers. Given the advancements in the electronic medium,

the rate of cybercrime victimisation during the stay-at-home order has grown (Kranenborg et al., 2019). According to research, perpetrators have developed a new ransomware known as "CoronaVirus" and a fraudulent browsing application (connected to medicine treating coronavirus) to encrypt end-user data. It was also revealed that most hackers try to share personal videos/photos of their victims, compose negative remarks about these individuals, or spam emails, interactive websites, malware, and Trojans to their victims during the stay-at-home order. (EUROPOL, 2020). The creation, distribution, or use of harmful software, such as malware or ransomware, is frequently considered a severe offence under the Computer Crime Act of 1997. For example, the dissemination of ransomware may result in severe sanctions since it involves extortion and possible financial loss to victims. Fines, jail, or both are possible penalties.

Moreover, most cybercrimes went unreported due to issues such as victims' unwillingness to come forward, fear of negative publicity, or confusion about where to report such instances. Underreporting might lead to the sense that cybercrime is not being addressed sufficiently. Evidently, in the case of cyberstalking, anonymity allows offenders to reach more potential victims with less chance of identification or punishment (Marganski, 2019). As a result, people on the receiving end tend to have a lower quality of life, likely to adjust their school or work-related routines, acquire poor psychological outcomes such as depression or anxiety, incur financial consequences, suicidal thoughts, or begin to distrust others (Marganski, 2019). It was stated that cyberstalking has long been infamously difficult to prosecute since most victims are hesitant to disclose such events owing to social ramifications (Marganski, 2019). Hence, reporting cybercrime and being aware of the issue at hand are critical, since reporting cybercrime assists law enforcement and cybersecurity specialists to take action to avoid potential collateral damage. By contributing knowledge of cyber risks through reporting events, allowing authorities to detect patterns, trends, and new attack vectors. Such information may be utilised to create preventative actions and strengthen cybersecurity defences.

3.3 Anonymity

The internet's obscurity has the potential to motivate users to engage in immoral behaviour. Cybercriminals can hide behind digital identities, making it difficult to track their movements and lowering their fear of being detected and held accountable. Due to the fact that anonymity allows cybercriminals to create and utilise fictitious identities, it is easier for them to impersonate people online. This may be used in a variety of cybercrimes, including identity theft, phishing, and social engineering crimes. Perpetrators can deceive victims by appearing as trustworthy entities, increasing susceptibility and allowing for effective exploitation. Most internet fraudsters used a well-planned and sophisticated technique to defraud their potential victims, especially when it occurred to fake lotteries, romance scams, gaming scams, and prize draw scams. (Ketchell, 2019). It is noticeable that individuals frequently become victims due to the art of persuasion (Broadhurst et al., 2020). For instance, many hackers construct fictitious female or male usernames in chat rooms to lure their victims in. Notably, people with female identities got an average of 100 threatening or sexually explicit messages each day, whereas males received just 3.5 messages per day (Nadim & Fladmoe, 2021). According to the Communication and Multimedia Act 1998, it forbids the publication of online content that is vulgar, indecent, false, threatening, or insulting in nature. This might be used to report online sexual harassment, vile comments, and threats of murder or rape. The conviction under section 233, an infraction under this section is punished by up to one year in jail, a fine of up to RM50,000, or both. Social Control Theory, on the other hand, explains why people respect laws and how behaviour conforms to societal expectations. According to Social Control Theory, internal limitations emerge during childhood, and crime develops as a result of inadequate constraints. In other words, free will provides offenders with the ability to choose and so take responsibility for their deviant action. The argument that online anonymity encourages permissiveness is supported by Social Control Theory. Individuals are obligated to stop from unlawful and deviant activity when social controls, such as social

ostracism and legislation, are present, according to Social Control Theory. However, deviation increases where controls or the perceived strength of controls are absent or reduced (Rogers, Siegfried, & Tidke, 2006).

Anonymity makes it challenging to pin down cybercrime to specific individuals or groups. Due to the use of anonymization techniques and worldwide reach, investigating agencies frequently confront challenges in tracing cybercriminal actions to real-world identities. It can be used by individuals with malicious intent to lure and exploit victims online. This can be seen in another case where several child sex offenders appeared to be the same age as the adolescents in order to easily approach them (Maras, 2019). Females are also readily enticed by perpetrators using a number of methods such as false promises of love relationships, falsified career prospects with high pay in another nation, or false pledges to make them more renowned. In addition to this, females are victimised by internet luring in a variety of ways, including gender-based slurs or harassment, cyberstalking, slut-shaming, sextortion, electronically facilitated trafficking, and unwanted pornography (Maras, 2019). Internet luring is defined as a deceptive practice in which individuals attempt to deceive their potential victims by using various online platforms such as chat rooms, employment websites, email, and et cetera. Therefore, the stated cases above justify why the anonymity of the internet and de-individualization in cyberspace can reduce self-regulation and lead to uninhibited behaviour.

3.4 Peer Influence or Subcultures

Peer influence may have a substantial impact on cybercrime, both encouraging and discouraging it. Peer standards and social pressure are important in moulding behaviour, including participation in cybercrime. Individuals may be more prone to participate in cybercriminal acts to fit in or acquire social status if such behaviours are regarded normal or even applauded within a certain peer group. Individuals may be discouraged from participating in cybercrime if their peer group strongly rejects it, for fear of social disapproval. Social pressure to conform causes us to act in ways that contradict or are incongruent with our inner convictions. (Ajzen, 1991). To some extent, the predatory influence of recession, exposure to low living standards, and an uncooperative socioeconomic atmosphere of their situation with people with comparable life chances. For example, the shared conditions of unemployment, poverty, pessimism, and a grim future elicit comparable emotions throughout the population in the group. In an unemployment perspective, one of the causes is that businesses may curtail or freeze hiring during periods of economic recession or slowdown, resulting in increased unemployment rates. This can be triggered by a variety of circumstances, including global economic conditions, financial crises, or changes in the business. According to Sobieralski (2020), travel limitations imposed by governments have had a significant influence on the mobility of people throughout the world, while also having a detrimental impact on various downstream businesses such as tourism, hospitality, and transportation. Flight cancellations and capacity cuts have forced the airline sector to struggle for survival. Due to numerous cash flow challenges during the one-year lockdown period due to COVID-19, certain domestically developed airlines, such as Malindo Air, had thrown up the towel, resulting in the bulk of its personnel losing their employment, with just 1000 staying employed (Ram 2020; Birruntha 2020).

As youths band together to build a shared path towards surviving an agonising socioeconomic catastrophe, the peer impact becomes more effective. For instance, a group of people stumbles onto a website that sells high-end equipment at ridiculously low costs. They urge each other to take advantage of the discount, despite their suspicions that the website is engaged in fraudulent operations. They then use stolen credit card information to make purchases and encourage others to do the same. Credit card fraud is commonly defined as the use of stolen credit card information without the cardholder's authorization. This can include making transactions online, in-person, or over the phone with stolen credit card information. Most incidents of credit card fraud that result in criminal charges are handled at the state and municipal levels. Fraud is prosecuted differently in various states. The severity of the

sentence is determined by a variety of variables, including the fraudster's previous past, the amount taken, and whether he or she has criminal intent. According to the Department of Justice, fraudulent credit card use can also be classified as computer fraud, mail fraud, wire fraud, and financial institution fraud, with penalties of up to 30 years in jail. Research has shown individuals are impacted not just by the behaviour of their significant others in the social context, but also by the behaviour of others with whom they have similar characteristics and dispositions (Philip & Cartensen, 1986).

3.5 User Dependence on Technology

Technological breakthroughs have permitted previously unimaginable levels of connectedness. People may communicate with one another internationally and get information by using the internet, wireless networks, and communication technologies. Technology, notably social media platforms, has transformed communication by giving immediate and simple means to communicate with people all over the world. People may now communicate with friends, family, and coworkers in real time, exchange updates, and engage in real-time dialogues, building a sense of togetherness and community. Furthermore, social media sites provide a wide range of entertainment alternatives, including films, games, and interactive material. They give a forum for self-expression, creativity, and the exchange of ideas with others. For many people, social media has become an essential element of their leisure activities. However, technology has its own setbacks. The rapid advancement of technology has made it increasingly difficult to detect cybercrimes. In fact, according to (Norton, 2016) 689 million people in 21 countries have experienced cybercrime in their daily lives in the past couple of years. This has made people equally fearful of online risks as they are of real-world risks. Indians are becoming the largest users of several mobile applications and websites, which has made it more challenging for security service providers to ensure safety. Cybercriminals take advantage of this by attacking online through fake apps by putting them in the play store. Such applications are intended to trick users and do dangerous actions. They may promise to provide services such as free downloads, game cheats, or access to exclusive material, but they infect devices with malware, steal personal information, or engage in fraudulent activities.

Mobile banking malware is becoming more sophisticated, and attackers are stealing more than just credit card data by staying under the radar and bypassing security mechanisms. According to Nilesh Jain, vice president, Southeast Asia and India, Trend Micro, "With banking increasingly becoming an integral part of mobile device usage, attackers have begun building more sophisticated capabilities into their mobile banking malware." One of the most famous cases of cybercrime in the virtual world is "The game Blue Whale challenges," created by 21-year-old Russian Phillip Bedecking. The game was played by children in the virtual world and claimed an estimated 130 lives across the world during 2015-2016. According to Symantec, 45% of the most popular Android apps and 25% of the most popular iOS apps request location tracking, 46% of popular Android apps and 24% of popular iOS apps request permission to access the device's camera, and email addresses are shared with 44% and 48% respectively. This highlights the importance of being cautious when granting permissions to apps. Consumers are more likely to experience cybercrime than get the flu, and 76% of consumers say they are more alarmed than ever about their privacy. Additionally, 95% believe that it's very important to require companies and organisations to give consumers control of their personal data, including 44% who believe it is necessary that companies do this, or consequently be fined. It's crucial for individuals to take necessary precautions and for companies to prioritise data privacy and security.

4. DISCUSSION

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

The relationship between criminals' ethical behaviour and the profit incentive in cybercrime is complicated and interconnected. For cybercriminals, the economic motivation, motivated by the desire for financial gain, frequently trump's ethical considerations. The chance of quickly and significantly increasing one's profits through acts such as hacking, identity theft, ransomware, and fraud can cause people to prioritise their own self-interest over ethical limits. Financial gain is one of the primary reasons for cybercriminals. To fool their victims and get sensitive information that may be monetized, they use numerous strategies such as phishing, online scams, and fraud. The allure of money advantages can distract criminals to the ethical ramifications of their activities, especially when there is a perceived minimal chance of detection or legal consequences. The profit motivation may be evident in situations of online purchase fraud, where individuals are duped by fraudulent online retailers, in the context of cybercrime. Profiteering, misleading representation, and selling counterfeit goods are all practices used by offenders to maximise their financial profits at the expense of unwary consumers. This exemplifies how profiteering may lead to immoral behaviour in the cyber sphere.

Furthermore, the unawareness of the consequences might contribute to ethical violations in cybercrime. Because of the worldwide nature of cybercrime and the constraints of jurisdictional concerns and enforcement capacity, cybercriminals may assume they are unlikely to be identified or suffer legal ramifications. The dynamic nature of cybercrime frequently outpaces the development of legal frameworks and enforcement procedures, making prosecution of perpetrators more difficult. This absence of penalties, or the perception of impunity, might motivate unethical behaviour in the quest of financial gain.

Additionally, Anonymity is a strong motivator for people to engage in unethical behaviour in cyberspace. Because of the internet's anonymity, cybercriminals may hide behind digital identities, making it harder to monitor and hold them accountable. This anonymity may be used to mimic others, which can lead to a variety of cybercrimes such as identity theft and phishing. The capacity to deceive victims by posing as trustworthy institutions boosts the success of cybercriminal actions, emphasising the relationship between anonymity and unethical behaviour even more.

Peer influences and subcultures can also impact cybercriminal behaviour. Individuals may participate in cybercrime due to social pressure and the desire to fit in or obtain social prestige within a certain peer group. Individuals may be more likely to engage in immoral behaviour if such behaviours

are normalised or celebrated within their social group. Individuals may be discouraged from participating in such behaviour if there is a strong condemnation of cybercrime within their peer group.

Last but not least, user dependence on technology and the rapid advancement of digital platforms have produced an environment conducive to cybercrime. The growing number of users and their dependency on mobile applications and websites has made it difficult for security service providers to assure their customers' safety. Cybercriminals take advantage of this by exploiting flaws in the technical infrastructure and targeting naive consumers with tactics such as mobile banking malware and bogus apps. The rise of personal data sharing and app permissions increases privacy and security issues, underscoring the need for consumers and businesses to prioritise data protection. Conclusively, the profit motive, unawareness of consequences, anonymity, peer influences, and user dependence on technology are all aspects that lead to ethical breaches in cybercrime. Understanding these dynamics is critical for designing successful measures to prevent cybercrime and encourage ethical digital behaviour. Education, knowledge, robust regulatory frameworks, and increased cybersecurity measures are critical in minimising the impact of profit-driven immoral behaviour in the cyber realm.

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

In conclusion, prioritising cybersecurity and information ethics is critical for people, organisations, and governments. Education and understanding of cybersecurity threats are critical for empowering consumers to protect themselves and avoid being victims of cybercrime. To dissuade cybercriminals and hold them accountable for their acts, legislative frameworks and enforcement tools must be strengthened. To safeguard individuals, organisations, and society as a whole from the dangers and repercussions of cybercrime, it is of the utmost importance to create a safer and more secure digital environment.

Preventing cybercrime necessitates being proactive and practising excellent digital hygiene. Look for phishing indications such as misspelt email addresses, generic welcomes, frantic requests for personal information, or unknown URLs. Furthermore, users should exercise caution while disclosing personal or sensitive information online. Avoid sharing too much personal information on social media networks, and restrict access to your profiles by adjusting privacy settings. Moreover, it is critical to remain up to date on the latest cyber threats and frequent frauds. Educate yourself on recommended practises for internet safety on a regular basis, such as spotting warning signals and adopting secure behaviours.

Acknowledgments: We would like to express our appreciation to Dr. Mohamad Rahimi Mohamad Rosman, the paper's co-author. He has guided us through the process of completing this research paper. This work is also supported through funding by the UiTM Campus Machang Academic Affairs via the KW3P system. This research paper would not have been completed without all the support provided to us.

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